

Diagnostic Challenges and Herbal Medicine Use in Irritable Bowel Syndrome (IBS) in Syria: A Cross-Sectional Study

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Abstract

Background:

Irritable Bowel Syndrome (IBS) is a common gastrointestinal disorder with complex interactions between psychosocial factors and gut function. This study explores the prevalence, diagnostic challenges, and herbal medicine use for IBS in Syria.

Methods:

A descriptive cross-sectional online survey was conducted between October 2022 and May 2023. A total of 927 participants from multiple Syrian governorates completed a questionnaire based on Rome IV criteria. Data were analyzed using Google Sheets, calculating frequencies, percentages, and diagnostic discrepancies including overdiagnosis and underdiagnosis.

Results:

The confirmed prevalence of IBS was 38.4% (n=356). Among these, only 51.7% (n=184) had previously received a formal medical diagnosis, while 140 previously diagnosed participants did not meet Rome IV criteria, highlighting potential overdiagnosis. Nine participants who neither suspected nor had a prior diagnosis were newly identified (underdiagnosis). Psychosocial stress was reported by 87.1% (n=318) of confirmed cases as a trigger for symptom exacerbation. Herbal medicine use was prevalent (81.2%, n=289), primarily *Cuminum cyminum* (47.2%, n=168) and *Mentha* (39.6%, n=141), mostly prepared as hot infusions.

Conclusion:

IBS in Syria is highly prevalent, with significant diagnostic inconsistencies. Standardized diagnostic protocols and evidence-based public health guidance for safe phytotherapy are urgently needed.

Keywords: Irritable Bowel Syndrome (IBS), Rome IV Criteria, Syria, Phytotherapy, Cuminum cyminum, Mentha, Psychosocial Factors, Diagnostic Gap

Materials and Methods

Study Design

A descriptive cross-sectional design was employed over eight months (October 2022–May 2023) to evaluate self-reported IBS symptoms, diagnostic discrepancies, and herbal medicine use among Syrians.

Participants and Data Collection

A structured electronic questionnaire was distributed via WhatsApp, Facebook, and Telegram. Participation was voluntary with electronic informed consent. 927 responses from multiple governorates were analyzed. No personal identifiers were collected.

Survey Instrument

1. Diagnostic Evaluation: Based on Rome IV criteria (minimum 6-month abdominal pain, association with defecation, and stool changes). Participants' prior physician diagnoses and self-suspected IBS were recorded to assess over- and underdiagnosis.
2. Management and Phytotherapy: Participants reported use of herbal remedies (Mentha, Cuminum cyminum, anise, ginger), preparation methods, and frequency of use.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using Google Sheets. Frequencies and percentages summarized demographic characteristics, prevalence, diagnostic discrepancies, and herbal medicine use. Special attention was given to previously diagnosed participants who did not meet Rome IV criteria.

Ethical Considerations and Informed Consent

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. Digital informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their participation in the online survey. Participants were informed about the study's purpose, the anonymity of their data, and their right to withdraw at any time. No identifiable personal information was collected.

Results

1. Demographic Characteristics

Female	718	77.4%
Male	209	22.6%
Mean Age	25 years	-
Total	927	100%

2. Prevalence of IBS and Diagnostic Gap

Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Confirmed IBS (Rome IV)	356	38.4%
Prior Clinical Diagnosis	184	51.7%*
Self-Suspected IBS	164	46.1%*
Unrecognized Cases (neither suspected nor diagnosed)	9	2.5%*

*Percentages calculated among confirmed IBS cases (n=356).

Key Observation – Diagnostic Inconsistency:

- 140 participants previously diagnosed by healthcare providers did not meet Rome IV criteria (overdiagnosis).
- 9 participants neither suspected nor had prior diagnosis were confirmed as IBS cases (underdiagnosis).

3. Psychosocial Correlates

Among confirmed IBS cases, 87.1% (n=318) reported symptom exacerbation during stressful periods.

4. Phytotherapeutic Practices

Herb	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Cuminum cyminum (Cumin)	168	47.2%
Mentha (Mint)	141	39.6%

80.9% prepared these herbs as hot infusions (tea).

5. Figure 1: Diagnostic Gap Visualization

Discussion

- IBS prevalence in Syria is high (38.4%), consistent with Middle Eastern estimates.
- Significant diagnostic discrepancy observed: overdiagnosis (140 participants) and underdiagnosis (9 participants).
- Psychosocial stress strongly associated with symptom exacerbation (87.1%).
- Herbal remedies widely used (81.2%), mainly cumin and mint; safe use requires public guidance.
- Highlights need for standardized diagnostic tools and integrated management including psychological support.

Study Limitations

- Sampling Bias: Predominantly female sample (77.4%).

- Data Collection: Online survey may exclude individuals without internet.
- Age Distribution: Mean age 25 years may limit generalizability to older populations.
- Self-Reported Data: Reliance on self-reported symptoms may introduce recall bias.
- Implications: Despite limitations, findings provide preliminary insights into IBS prevalence, diagnostic gaps, psychosocial factors, and phytotherapy use in Syria. Future studies should use representative samples and clinical evaluation.

Conclusion

- IBS is highly prevalent in Syria with diagnostic inconsistencies.
- Psychological stress is a major factor; herbal remedies are widely used.
- Standardized diagnosis, psychological support, and safe phytotherapy guidance are recommended.

Author Contributions

The author was solely responsible for the study conception, design, data collection, statistical analysis, and drafting of the manuscript. The author has read and approved the final version of the manuscript.

Competing Interests

The author declares that there are no financial or personal relationships that could have inappropriately influenced the writing of this article. No potential competing interests exist.

Data Availability

The raw data supporting the findings of this study are available from the author upon reasonable request.

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